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HEALTH REFORMS IN NAMANGAN REGION

***Annotation:** The article covers health institutions in the Namangan region during the years of independence, their activities in providing medical services to the population. Also, the work carried out on the existing problems and their elimination was laid out through archival materials and the necessary resources.*

***Keywords:** Health, medical institutions, Polyclinic and outpatient, laboratory equipment, medical equipment.*

Thanks to independence, direct relations were established with the countries of the world. Among the humanitarian aid to Uzbekistan, the emphasis on medicine has gained special importance. Non-governmental organizations abroad made a significant contribution to the work of medicines, sanitation in addition to equipment, the provision of drinking water to remote villages. And once the focus on private ownership has been increased, business investors are doing the work of building medical masks and providing equipment on the basis of sponsorship.

At the very beginning of independence, issues of providing medical care to citizens, strengthening sanitary and preventive service, improving quality and efficiency, especially protecting the lives of pregnant women and children of childbearing age were among the priorities.

In the events of the program "Ecology and health" for 1994-1995, great attention was paid to the creation of conditions for the upbringing of a healthy generation, protection of the environment and public health. In the early years of independence, medical examinations under the state program for the recovery of women, especially when extragenital disorders were detected in women of childbearing age, were carried out in the region with a separate list and operational work on recovery. In the region, shortness of breath, diseases of the digestive organs, diseases of the blood and blood – producing organs were detected. In the midst of infectious diseases, viral hepatitis disease became especially acute in 1995.

In the regions of the region, landscaping and greening months, ecological decada and Saturdays, lectures and conversations, competitions, a pictorial exhibition, the organization of charitable events have become a dish. Organizational measures have been implemented to protect and use water resources wisely, improve the quality of drinking water.

A proportional situation began to arise in the processes of birth, death and natural growth in relation to the population. From the initial period of independence, the adoption of the "for a healthy generation" program and

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relentless efforts were made along the way. Research on improving the nation, prolonging the life of the population, reducing the death of mothers and children, leaving healthy and talented offspring to future generations has proven that this area is the right one.

In the years of independence, the path of the extensive development of the health system was abandoned and switched to a path of continuous intensive improvement. The number of disadvantaged and inefficient patient beds has been reduced. The number of seats per population was reduced from 10 to 6.1. This in turn provided an opportunity to improve the treatment conditions of patients. Ten years ago in hospitals to one patient

While 2.5-3 square meters of space corresponded, in 2000 this figure was 8-10 m². In turn, the bulk of the funds allocated to medicine (50 percent) were spent on the Prevention of diseases and the treatment of patients in outpatient-Polyclinic conditions. The structure of maternity hospitals was formed with fundamentally new departments – prenatal Wellness, a maternity Hall and departments that restore the health of the mother-child after childbirth.

The health of the younger generation, above all, is in the hands of mothers, and in this regard, the decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the social protection of pregnant women and children under two years of age was a timely document. Over the past 1.5 years in the Fergana region on the implementation of the decree, measures have been taken to improve the health of pregnant women living in the village and free feeding of children under 2 years of age .

Difficulties arose in providing the population with medicines, for the positive solution of which 5 small enterprises were created by the Regional Health Department and the Production Association "Farmasiya" with the direct help of the regional authorities. According to the results of the experiment, medicinal plants were grown on 30 hectares of land, the production of more than 10 medicines has been established. However, the hospital's supply of medicines was 55 percent, only . In order to further improve the supply of the drug, 219 of the 234 pharmacies planned in the Fergana region were privatized on the basis of resolution 132 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan of March 11, 1994.

The infant mortality rate for every thousand children in Namangan region was 34.9 in 1993, while it decreased to 29.7 in 1994. The maternal mortality rate was reduced from 34.9 to 29.8. The 1995 provincial health system was served by 4,722 doctors, more than 16,500 intermediate medical personnel . As a result of the work carried out, the rate of maternal and child mortality decreased from year to year. Maternal mortality was 39.1 in 1992, 34.9 in 1993, 29.7 in 1994, and infant mortality under one year The death rate of children under the age of 39.8 in 1992, 34.9 in 1993, achieved a decrease of 29.7 in 1994, or 14 years from 5.0 in 1994 compared to 1992 3.2 down. From 1992-1994, a number of medical facilities were operated, including 5 medical points, 2 paramedic-obstetric points,

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6 rural-medical outpatient clinics, 3 Modern project polyclinics for 1,140 trips, specialized 225 special-bed hospitals with a total of 700 seats, and pharmacy buildings were built and put into operation .

1994 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan. In 1994 to fulfill the decision of the Ministry of health of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 132 "on the nationalization and privatization of pharmacy institutions" dated March 11 195 pharmacy institutions were nationalized .

Studies on the adoption of the program" for a healthy generation " and the incessant struggle along the way, the recovery of the nation, the extension of the life of the population, the reduction in the death of mothers and children have proven that the right way is done in this area to leave healthy and talented offspring to future generations.

Experiments of advanced countries began to be used in the training and attestation of doctors. A physician training program was introduced using the tried and tested methods of medical care. The fact that fifteen doctors, a little less than sixty moderately qualified employees per thousand inhabitants, is a sign that bold steps are being taken in this area in the country. The instructions of the head of the country to strengthen the medical service in the village itself fulfilled the longing of our people for a long time.

Despite the decrease in maternal and child mortality in the Valley provinces during the period under study, maternal and child mortality remained on the agenda as a major problem in the system. This is due to the fact that the level of medical care for rural residents is not at the level of medical care provided to citizens of the city. More than 60% of the rural population was provided with primary care in faps, mainly by an intermediate medical officer. Second, of the primary medical facilities in the village

Over 56% were housed in adapted buildings. Their 37% did not have a refrigerator, and 55% did not have a tap water supply . As a result, 16 women died in childbirth in the province in 1994. Such an unpleasant situation was 20 in 1993.

In turn, in the domestic market, the necessary measures were taken to meet the needs of the population for medicines. But, without the development of the National Pharmaceutical Industry, life itself clearly showed that it is impossible to solve this problem without establishing the production of medicines at the expense of local raw materials with reliable partners abroad. A period of competition has also come in the medical field. As a result of a number of positive works in the Valley provinces, infant mortality rates have been decreasing year by year.

An increase in infant mortality in Namangan region was observed in Yangiqoorgan district. The reason is that a specialist physician (neonatologist) did not work in the maternity ward of the District Central Hospital. This situation was studied by The Specialists of the region and the chief neonatologist of the Republic, and it was required to put specialists in place . In particular, child deaths between the ages of 1-2 were higher in Namangan, Chortoq and Kosonsoy

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districts, child deaths between the ages of 0-5 were higher in Namangan and Kosonsoy districts, and child deaths between the ages of 0-14 were higher in Namangan district. In the province, 4 mothers died in 2000 and 5 mothers in 2001 during the process of having children. Of these, 4 were rural and 6 had their first children. Considering that the main part of these women was the housekeeper, he indicated among them the need to further strengthen health care.

Namangan region had a population of 1 million 991,900 by this time. Of the total population, 992,800 (49.8 percent) were female, of whom 461,662 (23.2 percent) were female reproductive age, and children under the age of 14 748,800 (37.6 percent), of which children under the age of 1 were 40,000 There were 180

The increase in the number of outpatient clinics, however, was in the growth of the need for medical services as a result of the growing demographic population in some areas. Also, the reforms carried out in the following years to establish private medical institutions and bring medical equipment from foreign countries led to an increase in the number of outpatient clinics.

In the present period, a lot of work is being done by the Countryman to reform the industry. Sh.In his speech at the inauguration of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan at the Joint Session of the House of Commons, Mirziyoev touched on the tasks of taking things to a new level, saying: "in order to preserve human health, which is an invaluable asset for us, the health sector, first of all, its units at the primary branch, radically improve the activities of, the implementation of a complex of measures for the further development of specialized special centers will be the center of attention of the government," he stressed.

Of course, such medical problems are also present in the Namangan region, and according to otolaryngologist Qambarova Nodirakhan Asgarovna, a doctor who lives in the Uchkurgan district, Heart, Vascular, oncological and endocrinological diseases in the region are now very common among the population. The reasons for the origin of the disease are irritability, tightness, non-compliance with a healthy lifestyle and improper nutrition .

Under the presidency of the president, on February 25, 2020, at the meeting of the reform of the health sector, Ibn Sina stated that schools would be established on the site of medical colleges, which remained in the old-fashioned way . After all, since the future of the country depends on the maturity of the younger generation, it is life itself that dictates the introduction of new approaches to raising them healthy.

At the initiative of the head of state, classes and practices are held in the schools of Ibn Sina on the basis of the requirements of the Times. The most important thing is that they teach a deep lesson from the views, recommendations of our greatness on the science of Medicine.

Due to the lessons of the pandemic, telemedicine was established between the specialized medical centers of the Republic and their branches on the spot, and the possibilities for diagnostics and treatment were further expanded.

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In order to bring medical service in villages and neighborhoods to a qualitatively new level, instead of a general practitioner, "medical brigades" consisting of a family doctor and 5 secondary medical personnel were established, and the work of the "family doctor" point and family polyclinics was established. Under the "rural doctor" program, more than a thousand doctors in remote areas who were taking El Dardi ointments were provided with 30 crores of aid and provided with service houses .

As part of activities aimed at increasing the status of middle-tier medical personnel, they are being provided with the opportunity to independently engage in "nursing". Graduates of the technicums named after Ibn Sina (47 in total) are targeted for careers in several fields of Medicine.

In 2020, the provision of quality medical services to the inhabitants of the villages of the Fergana Valley was further improved. For example, certain work has been done to take the work of the health system to a new level in Namangan, especially to further improve the functioning of the primary joint. In addition, efforts to improve the quality of medical services provided to existing villagers, to achieve people's approval of medical services, ultimately resulted in positive results. At the family doctor's point "Shahidon" in the district of turakurghan, more than 8 thousand people were responsible for ensuring the health of the population, and in April of this year, citizens living in three neighborhoods located in the area were subjected to medical correspondence and anthropometric measurements . The non-governmental sector of Medicine has also developed rapidly in the region. Their number increased sharply from year to year, and the scope of Service also expanded. It was in the center of this district that the private hospital "Hayat medical", specializing in 40 seats, contributed to the restoration of the health of the villagers here.

In order to treat oncogemotology, endocrine diseases, special departments were created in regional hospitals. Thirty-five inter-district centers for acute vascular diseases were established. The lives of many people were saved by the rapid and qualified medical care of the population of these centers in cases of heart attacks and strokes. Also, medical tourism is developing in the Valley regions, as in the Republic today.